

Table 1. Resistance to RSV in field and artificial inoculation tests.

Line/F ₁	Percent infection	
	Field ^a	Inoculation ^b
Norin 25	92.4 + 1.5 b	90.2 + 3.9 c
Tjina	0.0 + 0.0 a	(no data)
BL 1	0.0 + 0.0 a	41.1 + 4.2 b
Nipponbare	90.9 + 2.6 b	94.9 + 4.5 c
Nipponbare/BL 1(F ₁)	0.0	63.6

^aData are means + SEM of three replicates. Nipponbare/BL 1 (F₁) and BL 1 were tested without replication. SEM = standard error of means. ^bData are means + SEM of seven replicates. Nipponbare/BL 1 (F₁) were tested without replication. Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ ($k = 100$) according to Waller-Duncan LSD.

Table 2. Relationship between RSV resistance and blast resistance in F₃ lines from Nipponbare and BL 1.

RSV incidence	Number of F ₃ lines ^a	Number of F ₃ lines with reaction to blast isolate Ken 54-20	
20.0–80.0 ^b	148	Resistant	31
		Segregating	79
		Susceptible	38
		χ^2 (1:2:1) = 1.338	
80.1–100.0	52	Resistant	12
		Segregating	27
		Susceptible	13
		χ^2 (1:2:1) = 1.338	
		χ^2 (1:2:1) = 1.240	
χ^2 (3:1) = 0.107			

^aNo chi-square values for goodness of fit to expected ratios were significant. The uniformity test was also not significant for segregation for blast resistance between high and low RSV incidence groups ($c^2 = 0.104$, $0.90 < P < 0.95$, $df = 2$). ^bMaximum RSV incidence was determined from the range of the susceptible parent, Nipponbare.

number of nymphs on Nipponbare and BL 1 was significantly higher than that on IR50 (resistant check). We concluded that BL 1 was susceptible to SBPH, although resistant to RSV, and that Nipponbare was susceptible to both (data not shown).

The inheritance of RSV resistance was studied by artificial inoculation using viruliferous SBPH and by serological assay using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. In the inoculation test on seedlings, the average infection percentage of RSV was 41.1 for BL 1, 94.9 for Nipponbare, and 63.6 for their F₁, suggesting that BL 1 resistance was incompletely dominant. The RSV incidence distribution in F₃ lines was multimodal with three peaks, indicating a single major genic segregation for resistance. To confirm this, we analyzed the

mode of inheritance biometrically. We estimated that an incompletely dominant gene controlled BL 1 resistance based on maximum likelihood ratios. These results also agreed with the chi-square goodness of fit test to a ratio of 3 (homozygous resistant and segregating):1 (homozygous susceptible) as expected by segregation of a pair of incompletely dominant genes (Table 2).

The segregation of all F₃ lines fitted a ratio of 1:2:1 as expected by the segregation of the *Pi-b* resistance gene. No relation was seen between RSV infection incidence and the blast resistance gene *Pi-b* segregation in F₃ lines (Table 2). We concluded that the locus of RSV resistance in BL 1 was independent of the *Pi-b* locus, estimated to be near the terminal region of chromosome 2.

We observed many progeny susceptible or segregating for resistance to RSV in F₃ lines ($n = 72$) between BL 1 and Musashikogane with *Stvb-i*. The segregation pattern of 70 (homozygous resistant and segregating):2 (homozygous susceptible) in RSV resistance fitted a 15:1 ratio as expected based on the genetic model of the two independently dominant genes. From these results, we concluded that BL 1 has a new resistance gene for RSV infection with incomplete dominance not linked to the *Pi-b* locus. The new resistance gene identified in BL 1 with improved plant type and blast resistance is considered useful in breeding for RSV-resistant cultivars in japonica rice.

Ischaemum rugosum—a potential alternate host of rice tungro viruses in West Bengal

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Carry-over of rice tungro disease (RTD) through seasons is one of the most important considerations in rice production, especially in India where the vector green leafhopper (GLH) (*Nephotettix* spp.) ap-

pears for a limited period of the year. In West Bengal, in boro rice (summer rice), which is transplanted in February-March and harvested in April-May, RTD incidence is very limited and found only in a few

pockets with an intensive rice-rice rotation. To search for alternate RTD hosts, we collected leaf samples of some weeds from an adjacent field severely infected with RTD during the 1995-96 boro season in the

Regional Research Station at Chakdaha of BCKV. Samples were tested by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (with assistance from IRRI) to determine the presence of two viruses associated with the disease. Leaf samples of the same weed hosts were also collected from nearby RTD-free rice fields for the control. In addition to serological testing, the survival period of GLH on weed hosts was also tested.

Serological testing of weed samples showed a positive reaction between rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) antisera and crude extracts from several weeds tested, except *Leersia hexandra*. Among the samples, *Ischaemum rugosum* and *Cyperus rotundus* had a strong positive reaction jointly with RTBV and RTSV antisera. The other two weeds, *Echinochloa colonum* and *Cynodon dactylon*, revealed lower reaction values. *I. rugosum* is commonly found in bunds in rice fields mostly in the Gangetic plains of West Bengal. Plants infected with tungro viruses did not develop any disease symptoms. The crude extract from control samples did not react with any of the antisera. No report is available on tungro infection by *I. rugosum*, which showed a high potential to act as a reservoir of RTD.

We conducted an experiment to determine GLH survival periods on these weed hosts under laboratory conditions. Samples of weed hosts were collected from rice fields and planted separately in earthen pots. Two GLH species, *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) and *N. nigropictus* (Stål), of the same age were released on potted weed hosts in mylar cages.

In general, the survival period of *N. nigropictus* on weed hosts was higher than that of *N. virescens* (see table). On *L. hexandra*, *N. nigropictus* survived up to 11 d, whereas *N. virescens* survived for only 4 d. Little variation in survival period of the two species of GLH was observed on *I. rugosum*, *C. rotundus*, and *E.*

colonum. *N. virescens* survived longer (14 d) on Taichung Native 1.

Positive ELISA results and GLH survival experiments for selected weeds, particularly *I. rugosum* and *C. rotundus*, will

allow us to conduct transmission experiments to confirm whether these weeds act as important alternate hosts for the virus between rice seasons.

ELISA reactions in rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) antisera and survival period of green leafhopper in some weed hosts collected from rice fields, West Bengal.

Host species	Percentage of reaction			Average survival (d) ^a	
	RTBV + RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	<i>N. virescens</i>	<i>N. nigropictus</i>
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	8.3	0.0	0.0	5.4 b	10.8 a
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>	6.7	0.0	46.7	3.2 bc	4.2 b
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	93.3	6.7	0.0	3.0 c	4.6 b
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	100.0	0.0	0.0	4.6 bc	4.0 b
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0 bc	11.0 a
Taichung Native 1	37.5	0.0	12.5	14.0 a	10.2 a
SEM				±0.77	±0.84
LSD at 0.05				2.28	2.47

^aAv values of 4 replications. Mean values in columns followed by a common letter do not differ significantly by Duncan's multiple range test ($P = 0.05$).

1999 IRRI calendar of training activities

2-Week Rice Production Training Course	18–29 Jan
Basic Experimental Design and Data Analysis	01–12 Feb
Hybrid Rice Breeding	01 Mar–23 Apr
Introduction to IRRISat Statistical Software	01–05 Mar
Introduction to SAS	26–30 Apr
Modern Rice Farming Course	03–28 May
Advanced Experimental Design	31 May–04 Jun
Instructional Video Production	07 Jun–02 Jul
Introduction to New Developments in G × E	
Analysis and Interpretation of Results	07–11 Jun
Analysis of Unbalanced Data	14–18 Jun
Analysis of Categorical Data	21–25 Jun
Rice Seed Health Training	05 Jul–24 Sep
Adaptive Research with a Farming Systems Perspective	19 Jul–27 Aug
Integrated Pest Management in Rice	02 Aug–24 Sep
Soil and Water Biochemistry and Ecotoxicology	23 Aug–10 Sep
Transgenic Rice: Production and Deployment	
with Special Reference to Sheath Blight and Rice	
Stem borer Resistance	27 Sep–17 Oct
Rice Production Research	04 Oct–26 Nov
Application of Molecular Tools to Study Rice Viruses	02 Nov–03 Dec